

Optimal procurement under backwardation and the benefits of the manifestation of demand aggregators

Ioannis Avramopoulos, Prodromos Makris, Emmanouel Varvarigos

^aNational Technical University of Athens, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, 9 Heron Polytechniou, Zographou, 15780, Attiki, Greece

Abstract

Normal backwardation manifests when the futures price of a commodity is below the expected future spot price. In this paper, we show how businesses can optimally leverage backwardation in their supply chain optimization. To that end, we derive the optimal amount a business ought to purchase in the futures market to take advantage of the favorable futures price in order to minimize the overall expected procurement cost. We further use Hoeffding's inequality to predict the manifestation of demand aggregators.

Keywords: optimization, normal backwardation, demand aggregators, procurement coalitions, decentralized markets

1. Introduction

In this paper, we provide an elementary solution to a fundamental problem in supply-chain optimization, namely, how to optimally accrue (reserve) an inventory of a perishable commodity under the assumption that the market for that commodity is in a state of normal backwardation. Normal backwardation manifests when the futures price of a commodity (resource) is below the expected future spot price and it is typical for soft commodities and perishable goods. Empirical data suggest that markets for perishable commodities are frequently in backwardation, and it is precisely this phenomenon that we aim to leverage toward the goal of supply-chain optimization.

To formulate the problem in more precise terms and fix the notation, we consider the following decision problem concerning a business \mathcal{B} facing the problem of procuring a commodity from a futures market and a spot market: \mathcal{B} has a demand D for a commodity (resource) at a future time T_1 .

At the present time T_0 , \mathcal{B} must decide what quantity to procure, while being uncertain of what demand will manifest at time T_1 . \mathcal{B} can certainly wait to purchase the resource at time T_1 paying the corresponding spot price \bar{p} . However, if the futures market is in a state of backwardation, \mathcal{B} can exploit this by planning ahead and procuring an amount of the resource at the lower futures price $p < \bar{p}$. In this paper, we derive the optimal amount $x \geq 0$ that \mathcal{B} can procure at the futures market at time T_0 under the assumption it knows the probability distribution of the demand that will manifest at time T_1 . We denote the cumulative distribution function of the demand by $F(\cdot)$ and the density function of the demand by $f(\cdot) \equiv F'(\cdot)$. The goal of \mathcal{B} is to minimize the overall expected procurement cost under the assumption that possible excess good ($D < x$) expires (perishes) after time T_1 and, thus, it cannot be sold again in the market to amortize the initial investment.

Our formulation is similar to the newsvendor problem, in which a decision maker facing a random demand for a perishable product must decide on the level of inventory of the product to stock for a single selling period [7]. In fact, the analytical expression that gives the optimal procurement strategy in our formulation (shown in Section 2) is also similar to the solution of the newsvendor problem. We believe there is no elementary transformation (mapping) that casts optimal procurement under backwardation as a newsvendor problem (and the contrary) and that optimal procurement under backwardation deserves a separate analytical treatment.

Drawing on Hoeffding’s inequality, we further show (in Section 3) that an implication of our result is that in a market for a resource under normal backwardation, it is optimal to form *demand aggregators*, that is, coalitions of businesses procuring the resource that share excess capacity using bilateral or multilateral resource sharing agreements. The benefit of such combined resource pools where excess capacity is shared is that they essentially absorb the risk of the actual cost being in excess of the expected cost, thus, insuring the market against demand uncertainty. The manifestation of demand aggregation is also predicted in theory in a similar model by [11] who consider a resource that can be reserved ahead of time at a lower price than the expected spot price under a “bursty” model of consumption (for example, when the resource being reserved is computing equipment/infrastructure). Our model can be viewed as a natural extension of that model and our theory predicts that procurement coalitions (i.e. demand aggregators) inexorably also develop in our extended setting.

In Section 4, we present a toy example that, based on a simple numerical

experiment, clearly demonstrates the benefits of forming demand aggregators (as predicted by Hoeffding's inequality). In Section 5, we further discuss related work and finally, in Section 6, we conclude and discuss future work.

2. The optimal procurement strategy

Let us denote the cost that \mathcal{B} faces by $C(x)$. Thus, the goal is to minimize the expected cost $E\{C(x)\}$. To that end, we proceed in two steps, namely, we first obtain an expression for $E\{C(x)\}$ that is amenable to optimization and then, in the second step, we optimize that expression. To that end, we have

$$E\{C(x)\} = E\{C(x)|D \leq x\}P\{D \leq x\} + E\{C(x)|D > x\}P\{D > x\}$$

and, since

$$E\{C(x)|D \leq x\} = px,$$

we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} E\{C(x)\} &= pxP\{D \leq x\} + E\{C(x)|D > x\}P\{D > x\} \\ &= pxF(x) + E\{C(x)|D > x\}(1 - F(x)), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where we have used the definition of the cumulative distribution function. Note now that

$$E\{C(x)|D > x\} = \frac{\int_x^{+\infty} C(y)f(y)dy}{\int_x^{+\infty} f(y)dy} = \frac{\int_x^{+\infty} C(y)f(y)dy}{1 - F(x)} \quad (2)$$

where $f(y) = F'(y)$. Therefore, combining (1) and (2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} E\{C(x)\} &= pxF(x) + \int_x^{+\infty} C(y)f(y)dy \\ &= pxF(x) + \int_x^{+\infty} (px + \bar{p}(y - x))f(y)dy \\ &= pxF(x) + (p - \bar{p})x \int_x^{+\infty} f(y)dy + \bar{p} \int_x^{+\infty} yf(y)dy \\ &= pxF(x) + (p - \bar{p})x(1 - F(x)) + \bar{p} \int_x^{+\infty} yf(y)dy \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= pxF(x) + (p - \bar{p})x + (\bar{p} - p)xF(x) + \bar{p} \int_x^{+\infty} yf(y)dy \\
&= -(\bar{p} - p)x + \bar{p}xF(x) + \bar{p} \int_x^{+\infty} yf(y)dy \\
&= -(\bar{p} - p)x + \bar{p}xF(x) + \bar{p} \int_0^{+\infty} yf(y)dy - \bar{p} \int_0^x yf(y)dy \\
&= -(\bar{p} - p)x + \bar{p}xF(x) + \bar{p}E\{D\} - \bar{p} \int_0^x yf(y)dy.
\end{aligned}$$

It is this latter expression that we sought to obtain in the first step. Moving now to the second step and taking the derivative with respect to x , we obtain

$$\frac{d}{dx}E\{C(x)\} = -(\bar{p} - p) + \bar{p}F(x) + \bar{p}xf(x) - \bar{p}xf(x) = -(\bar{p} - p) + \bar{p}F(x)$$

Taking further the second derivative with respect to x , we obtain

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2}E\{C(x)\} = \bar{p}f(x) \geq 0.$$

Therefore, $E\{C(x)\}$ is a convex function of x . Thus, the optimal x is obtained at

$$x^* = F^{-1}\left(\frac{\bar{p} - p}{\bar{p}}\right).$$

3. The optimality of demand aggregation under backwardation

The analysis in the previous section assumes that the procurement of an excess amount of resource at time T_0 relative to the (unknown) demand that manifests at time T_1 is lost (perishes). If the amount procured at time T_0 , namely, x , exceeds the actual demand D that manifests at time T_1 (that is, $D < x$), then business \mathcal{B} has an excess quantity of the resource equal to $x - D$. Instead of letting that quantity perish, it is beneficial for \mathcal{B} to share that quantity with other businesses.

Consider a pair \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 of businesses that decide to form a coalition aggregating their demand for their mutual benefit. A question of interest is how significant are the benefits that can be materialized. Hoeffding's inequality provides an answer to this question as shown below.

Let us assume for simplicity that the demands of \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 are independent and identically distributed and that this is known to both \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 . (For example, \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 infer the distribution of their demand from historical data and they make an agreement to share that data with each other.) Let us further assume that the (common) demand is upper bounded, for example, by 1. If \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 procure the resource unilaterally, Hoeffding's inequality gives that the probability the actual cost $C(x)$ exceeds the expected cost $E\{C(x)\}$ by an amount $c > 0$ is given by the following expression:

$$P \{C(x) - E\{C(x)\} \geq c\} \leq \exp\{-2c^2\}.$$

Suppose now that \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 decide to join forces. Although there are a variety of possible agreements \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 can make, let us assume they agree to split the final cost of their aggregated demand (using side payments) under the assumption that either will procure an amount of the resource equal to the amount they would have procured had they not formed the coalition. Such an agreement is fair by the symmetric position each business has in the coalition and the analysis of such a simple agreement provides an upper bound of the benefits that can manifest under aggregation.

Let us denote the cost \mathcal{B}_1 incurs by $C_1(x)$ and the corresponding cost \mathcal{B}_2 incurs by $C_2(x)$. These costs are independent and identically distributed random variables, by the assumption that the corresponding demands are independent and identically distributed random variables.

Being interested in the *average* cost obtained by splitting (in half) the aggregate cost that is obtained, the probability that such average actual cost $(C_1(x) + C_2(x))/2$ exceeds the average expected cost $E\{(C_1(x) + C_2(x))/2\}$ by the same amount $c > 0$ as above is given by the following expression:

$$P \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (C_1(x) + C_2(x)) - E \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (C_1(x) + C_2(x)) \right\} \geq c \right\} \leq \exp\{-4c^2\}.$$

That is, the probability the actual average cost will exceed the expected average cost has dropped exponentially. More generally, if there are n (independent and identically distributed) businesses $\mathcal{B}_1, \dots, \mathcal{B}_n$, we obtain the expression:

$$P \left\{ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n C_i(x) - E \left\{ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n C_i(x) \right\} \geq c \right\} \leq \exp\{-2nc^2\}.$$

That is, the probability the actual average will exceed the expected average drops exponentially with the number n of (homogeneous) businesses (of independent demand) entering the coalition.

The benefit of forming coalitions (under the splitting agreement that we have outlined above) is not materialized in the expectation of the cost incurred by the businesses (note, however, that under an agreement whereby their aggregate capacity is shared benefits are certain to materialize since we assume that the businesses adopt optimal procurement strategies), but rather in the deviation of the actual cost from the expected average, a phenomenon which is typical in risk management using insurance policies. We believe that the previous analysis provides ample justification for the formation of aggregated resource pools, however, this is not the end of the story as in a shared resource pool, it is profitable for a business to misrepresent the distribution of its demand to free ride on the expenses procured by other businesses. Negotiating contracts for the formation of combined resource pools exploiting the previous phenomenon is an interesting question for the future.

4. A numerical example

Let us consider a toy example to illustrate the previous analysis. Suppose, to that end, that there is a business \mathcal{B}_1 whose demand is uniformly distributed between 0 and 1. Suppose further that the futures price is $p = 1$ and that the expected future spot price is $\bar{p} = 2$. Then the optimal procurement amount is $1/2$ and the average cost is

$$2\frac{1}{2} - 2 \int_0^{1/2} y dy = 1 - \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{4},$$

which is an improvement over the average cost of 1 that \mathcal{B}_1 would have to incur without taking advantage of the futures market. Analytically computing the probability that the actual cost does not exceed the expected cost by an amount, say $1/8$, is a little harder than necessary in this simple example, but rather simple to estimate numerically. A straightforward numerical experiment gives that the empirical probability the actual cost does not exceed the expected cost by $1/8$ over 10^6 runs is 0.312. Suppose now two i.i.d. businesses \mathcal{B}_1 and \mathcal{B}_2 join forces under the terms we laid out in the previous section. A similarly straightforward numerical experiment gives that the

empirical probability the actual average cost does not exceed the average expected cost by $1/8$ over 10^6 runs is 0.304, which is an improvement over the scenario where the businesses act unilaterally. Going a step further, when three i.i.d. businesses \mathcal{B}_1 , \mathcal{B}_2 , and \mathcal{B}_3 join forces, the corresponding empirical probability goes even further down to 0.239. This clearly demonstrates the benefits of demand aggregation even in this toy example.

5. Other related work

Our work relates naturally, firstly, to *reservation contracts* and, secondly, to mechanisms for stable *procurement-coalition formation*.

5.1. Reservation contracts

There is a rich literature on the paradigm of buyers and sellers entering reservation contracts to hedge against demand and spot price uncertainties (for example, see [10, 1, 8, 9] and references therein) and, to a great extent, our work falls in the purview of that line of work: Our model can be used to optimally procure any resource whose seller issues reservation and spot prices such that the reservation price is lower than the spot price. This arrangement is explored, as mentioned earlier, in [11]. With respect to that work our newsvendor-type analysis is more general (and both models predict aggregation). In contrast to other previous work on reservation contracts, our techniques can optimally leverage established futures markets (under backwardation) without bilateral negotiations between buyers and sellers.

Reservation contracts act against demand and spot price uncertainties. Demand aggregation can further act as an additional layer of protection against such demand and spot price uncertainties. An interesting question for the future is to explore the introduction of intermediaries (demand aggregators) in the reservation-contracts landscape—our analysis suggests this is meaningful and also constitutes a theoretical prediction (awaiting verification or refutation) that aggregators are bound to manifest in this landscape.

5.2. Coalition formation

In this paper, we make the case that the manifestation of procurement coalitions under backwardation is technically meaningful and, in principle, beneficial for the individual actors and organizations that are incentivized to jointly coordinate their activities. Leveraging our techniques, organizations are meant to further build on an existing body of literature on the specific

mechanisms that coalitions can leverage to ensure the optimality and stability of their operations [6, 2]. For example, [6] outlines the need for stable farsighted coalitions focusing, thus, on the trade-off between the stability of the coalition’s members versus the minimization of expected costs over a given time horizon. This stable farsighted coalition concept is well-suited in decentralized markets (one of our main application domains) because a demand aggregator’s market power can considerably affect the market equilibrium. Indeed, in a recent related work [2], it is showcased how the strategic market behavior (bidding) of demand aggregators (DAs) can impact the market equilibrium. In particular, it is shown that there is a trade-off between each individual DA’s cost minimization (in the short term) and the market power that it may exercise being part of a larger coalition of DAs in the long term.

6. Concluding remarks

The principle of using reservations to hedge against demand and spot price uncertainties manifests in a variety of markets such as in agricultural soft commodities, energy markets, in internet communication networks (as expressed in service-level agreements between internet service providers), in optical networks (for example, see [3]), in aviation, etc. Our paper is the first to obtain a mathematically rigorous analysis treating in parallel the phenomenon of *backwardation* in futures markets and that of the manifestation of *reservation options* in supply chains. In fact, let us observe that these economic phenomena are intimately related in that (1) backwardation often manifests for perishable commodities and (2) reservation contracts often manifest in products that have a short lifecycle (for example, in electronics markets [1]). These observations and our analysis suggest that the thought experiment of establishing futures markets for, for example, electronic products (such as computers), treating them on par with other commodities traded in futures markets, is certainly worthy of further pursuit.¹

Centralized markets have high liquidity, strong market power concentration and institutional hedging mechanisms that reduce backwardation effects. In contrast, our work is aligned with emerging decentralized markets (e.g., IoT-edge computing markets [4], local energy markets [5] and other related

¹A main motivation for our research in this paper was how to bootstrap computer “clouds” in the center and at the edges of the internet.

digital marketplaces) due to higher risk exposure, lack of strong market-making mechanisms and reliance on smart contracts for automated trading.

In fact, the problem of bootstrapping IoT-edge-cloud computing infrastructures was (as mentioned elsewhere) one of our main motivations for taking up this research topic. By integrating the proposed normal backwardation principles into the above-mentioned decentralized market paradigms, market participants can optimize pricing, hedge risks and create a more efficient and resilient decentralized ecosystem. We note though that our analysis is abstract enough to admit generalizations to any perishable commodity, for example, in the agriculture sector, energy sector and elsewhere.

We aim to extend this work’s theoretical results by evaluating various optimal procurement strategies based on key parameters such as, demand and expected future spot price volatilities, correlation between demand and expected future spot prices, degree of risk aversion, size and market power of procurement coalitions in various market settings, etc. Another thread of our future work is to integrate our research results in the HEU-funded project’s [4] real-life use cases in collaboration with consortium’s industrial partners.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Professor John Tsitsiklis for feedback that helped improve the quality of this manuscript. This work was supported in part by European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 101136024 through Project EMPYREAN, and in part by European Union’s Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking (KDT-JU) under Grant Agreement 101097560 through CLEVER project.

References

- [1] V. Martinez de Albeniz and D. Simchi-Levi. Competition in the supply option market. *Operations Research*, 57(5):1082–1097, 2009.
- [2] A. Khaksari, K. Steriotis, P. Makris, G. Tsaousoglou, N. Efthymiopoulos, and E. Varvarigos. Electricity market equilibria analysis on the value of demand-side flexibility portfolios’ mix and the strategic demand aggregators’ market power. *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 38:101–399, 2024.

- [3] P. Kokkinos, P. Soumplis, and E. A. Varvarigos. Pattern-driven resource allocation in optical networks. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 16(2):489–504, 2019.
- [4] A. Kretsis, P. Kokkinos, and E. Varvarigos et al. Emphyrean: Trustworthy, cognitive and ai-driven collaborative associations of iot devices and edge resources for data processing. In *Proceedings of the 33rd International Symposium on High-Performance Parallel and Distributed Computing*, HPDC '24, page 385–388, New York, NY, USA, 2024.
- [5] I. Mamounakis, N. Efthymiopoulos, P. Makris, D. J. Vergados, G. Tsaousoglou, and E. Varvarigos. A novel pricing scheme for managing virtual energy communities and promoting behavioral change towards energy efficiency. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 167:130–137, 2019.
- [6] M. Nagarajan and G. Sošić. Stable farsighted coalitions in competitive markets. *Manage. Sci.*, 53(1):29–45, January 2007.
- [7] N. C. Petruzzi and M. Dada. Pricing and the newsvendor problem: A review with extensions. *Operations Research*, 73(2):183–194, 1999.
- [8] D. A. Serel. Optimal resource acquisition policy for a newsvendor under supply risk. *The Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 65(11):1748–1759, 2014.
- [9] S. Wang, H. Zhang, Y. Xu, and W. Tong. Online procurement with risk hedging. *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, 164, 2022.
- [10] D. J. Wu and P. R. Kleindorfer. Competitive options, supply contracting, and electronic markets. *Management Science*, 51(3):452–466, 2005.
- [11] F. Wu, L. Zhang, and B. A. Huberman. Truth-telling reservations. *Algorithmica*, 52:65–79, 2008.